

Short name	EU CCS Directive Operationalization	Long name	Operationalisation of Directive 2009/31/EC on the geological storage of carbon dioxide (+ amending Directives) in member states
Geographical scope	European Union (+ Norway)		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	The EU Directive provides a legal framework for the safe geological storage of CO ₂ within the EU, including risk assessment and liability determination. Member states (MS) have the authority to decide whether to allow or prohibit geological storage within their own territory. This Directive follows the regular legislative process between the EU and MS, which involves the Directive being put into national law and all MS informing the Commission of their transposition measures. As of the latest implementation report dated October 2019, 16 MS are fully conforming to the Directive.		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MS that are not yet conforming to the Directive may fail to adhere to common monitoring and reporting standards • Diverging national legislation risks causing inconsistencies in the tracking of carbon flows due to diverging definitions and monitoring practices (the EU Directive serves as a common denominator) • The Directive only applies to EU states, so any collaborations (Partnerships/Joint infrastructure) with non-MS countries should be based on agreements and provisions that ensure consistency with regard to MRV 		
Other issues this affects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MRV Readiness • Liability in hubs 		
Reference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Parliament; Council (2009): Directive 2009/31/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the geological storage of carbon dioxide and amending Council Directive 85/337/EEC, European Parliament and Council Directives 2000/60/EC, 2001/80/EC, 2004/35/EC, 2006/12/EC, 2008/1/EC and Regulation (EC) No 1013/2006 • European Commission (n.d.): Implementation of the CCS Directive, website • European Commission (n.d.): A legal framework for the safe geological storage of carbon dioxide, website • Deutscher Bundestag (2022): Evaluierungsbericht der Bundesregierung zum Kohlendioxid-Speicherungsgesetz, Drucksache 20/5145 • UCL (n.d.): CO₂ transport for storage: Regulatory regimes, website 		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Shogenova, A.; Piessens, K.; Holloway, S. et a. (2014): <u>Implementation of the EU CCS Directive in Europe: Results and Development in 2013</u>
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